

Additional file 7: Example of Child assessment feedback summary for teachers

Born in Bradford: The Primary School Years

[Redacted]

Handedness: Right

[Redacted]
Date of Test: 24/01/2019

SNAPSHOT

This report should not be used as a screening or predictive tool, rather as a snapshot of the child's development at this point in time.

